

Figure 4C: P-S6, P-ERK blot

2min p-erk
Figure 4C Arrows indicate lanes used in Figure 4C

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1,
Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2, Lane 4: Sib: Sib-3 C2 NI1 , Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2
Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

2min p-erk

P-ERK

1/15/04

Figure 4C: GAPDH for P-S6 blot

Phospho blot

REC1

3

Figure 4C Arrows indicate lanes used in Figure 4C

- Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1,**
- Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2, Lane 4: Sib: Sib-3 C2 NI1 ,
- Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2 Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2,
- Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4C: Total S6 Blot

Quick check

gel 3/4

total 5-6

I-S6

Figure 4C

Arrows indicate lanes used in Figure 4C

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1,
 Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2, Lane 4: Sib: Sib-3 C2 NI1 , Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2
 Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Fam 1012 Blot
total blot
Setz

Setz Akt + S6 blot ERK blot
5 sec
total blot gel 41

Figure 4C Arrows indicate lanes used in Figure 4C

Figure 4C: GAPDH for Total S6 blot

Lane 1: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 2: I-ASD-3 C1, NI1,
Lane 3: Sib-3 C1 NI2, Lane 4: Sib: Sib-3 C2 NI1 , Lane 5: Sib-3C2, NI2
Lane 6: I-ASD-3 C1, NI2, Lane 7: I-ASD-3 C2, NI1, Lane 8: I-ASD-3 C2 NI2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows